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Annotation

The chronotope problem is the most researched concept today. This article explores the literary space and time in Tahir Malik's fantastic stories. The space and time described in the stories "Davron", "Falak", "Hunting" and the skills of the writer are analyzed in detail. Tahir Malik's style of creating a fantastic story is also discussed.

Key words: chronotope, space and time, literary studies, genre poetics, nature of images, style, plot of an artistic work, composition, language, structure of an artistic text.

QISSALARDA ZAMON VA MAKONNING POETIK TASVIRI

Annotatsiya

Xronotop masalasi bugungi kunda eng ko'p tadqiq qilinayotgan tushuncha hisoblanadi. Mazkur maqolada Tohir Malikning fantastik qissalaridagi adabiy makon va zamon tadqiq etilgan. "Davron", "Falak", "Ov" qissalarida tasvirlangan makon va zamon, yozuvchining mahorati batafsil tahlil qilingan. Tohir Malikning fantastik qissa yaratish uslubi haqida ham fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: xronotop, makon va zamon, adabiyotshunoslik, janr poetikasi, obrazlar tabiati, uslub, badiiy asar syujeti, kompozitsiyasi, tili, badiiy matn strukturasi.

ПОЭТИЧЕСКОЕ ОПИСАНИЕ ВРЕМЕНИ И ПРОСТРАНСТВА В ПОВЕСТЯХ

Аннотация

Проблема хронотопа сегодня является наиболее исследованной концепцией. В данной статье исследуется литературное пространство и время в фантастических рассказах Тахира Малика. Подробно анализируются пространство и время, описанные в рассказах "Даврон", "Фалак", "Охота", а также мастерство писателя. Обсуждается также стиль Тахира Малика в создании фантастического рассказа.

Ключевые слова: хронотоп, пространство и время, литературоведение, жанровая поэтика, характер образов, стиль, сюжет художественного произведения, композиция, язык, структура художественного текста.

Introduction. The study of the creative heritage, spiritual and mental world of each writer, creator, and poet in our literature is one of the urgent tasks of our literary studies. The interpretation of the genre poetics, the nature of the images, the language, and the unique style of the stories of the writer Tahir Malik serves to strengthen our national spirituality.

Analysis of literature on the topic. In Uzbek literary studies, the work of certain writers, the spiritual world of people in their works, the diversity of characters, the plot and composition of the work of art, language, and style are topics that continue to be studied. In particular, Tahir Malik's work "Shaytanat" has been partially studied in articles published by U.Normatov, A.Rasulov, and A.Ulugov. However, in the studies conducted since the 20th century to this day, the interpretation of other stories by Tahir Malik has not been sufficiently studied.

It should be noted that in reality, time, limited by the human mind, constitutes a whole, an astronomical series, such as eras, centuries, years, seasons, months, weeks, days, hours... Space, on the other hand, represents a whole, such as the sky, earth, sea, desert... In order to increase the

credibility of the events they describe, creative people use this astronomical time and space in different ways, depending on their worldview and skill. In other words, in a work of art, time, space, space move from a physical content to a literary-philosophical essence. Tadqiqot metodologiyasi.

The problems of time and space, recognized as important categories of philosophy, are not alien concepts for fiction. In works of fiction, events and phenomena that occurred at a certain time and in a certain space find their expression. Chronotope is derived from the Latin word, which means *chronos* - time and *topos* – space. In literary criticism, the reference to the problem of time and space, that is, chronotope, began in the first half of the 20th century. This term was introduced into literary criticism by M. Bakhtin in the 30s of the 20th century. After M. Bakhtin, the problem of chronotope was studied by Y.M. Lotman [3], V. Ye. Khalizev [6], N.D. Tamarchenko [5]. In order to deeply understand the writer's artistic world, it is necessary to summarize the spatial and temporal boundaries reflected in his individual works, study their interconnected aspects and imagine them as a single whole. Because they themselves are actually aspects of the entire artistic world created by the artist [7]. M. Bakhtin, introducing the concept of chronotope into science, takes into account that it encompasses important parts of the genre, composition, plot, artistic text structure, and poetics of images at the heart of the work of art, and that it harmoniously reflects artistic space and time [2]. "We call the harmony between time and space, artistically perceived in literature, a chronotope..." writes M. Bakhtin [1]. In fact, a poetic phenomenon that harmoniously displays the genre, composition, plot, text structure, and images in a work of art is called a chronotope.

Analysis and results. In Tahir Malik's stories, space and time are also depicted as a whole. In fantasy works, heroes are launched into space, travel to foreign lands, but in Tahir Malik's works, they travel to history. In the fantasy story "Falak", the main character travels to history on a device created by Jahongir, that is, to the 15th century using a device called *elalloma*. The work describes the era in which Mirzo Ulugbek lived, and the scientists of that time. A fantasy writer must convincingly present a serious scientific hypothesis and idea as if it had come true. If a writer does not reflect the problems of the present era in his works, the social significance of his work will be lost. The writer always feels the era and time. Even when he refers to the past, he imbues the work with the problems of today. Thus, the story describes the events of two eras in parallel - the 15th and 20th centuries.

Tahir Malik's story "Hunting" is a fantasy work. Through fiction, the writer observes our motherland through the eyes of alien astronauts and writes about the sad fate of the victims of repression. In the story "Falak", Tahir Malik connected fiction with history. In "Ov" he also turned to history. In both stories, the experience and skill of the accomplished writer are clearly reflected. In the story, four people who were unjustly arrested and imprisoned in the same barracks meet. All of them are political prisoners, that is, "enemies of the people", but their worldview, thoughts, and beliefs are completely different, they even reject each other.

In the fantastic story "Davron", the events take place in Yozyavon. Archaeologists find golden human statues during excavations. The subsequent events of the work develop in this vein. The story tells about Davron, his teacher Bekmirzayev, Davron's classmate Niyoz Mansurov, and his leading relative. In the story, Niyoz and Davron talk about the people of the valley: "... – The people of the valley are incomprehensible. They are extremely polite. They are like butterflies around the guest. But I would say that they do not respect you from the heart. Is their courtesy fake?"

– You judge everything by your own merit. You are treated with false respect, even some of your actions are fake. You do not do good to anyone from the heart. That is why you are always suspicious of others.

– Why didn't you tell them who I am?

– They don't care. They have nothing to do with your actions. You are a guest, that's all!" [4]. Most of Tahir Malik's works take place in Andijan and its various districts. Since the writer's mother and uncle were from the valley, he probably vividly depicted the valley in his works. Elements of the valley dialect are also noticeable in the language of the characters. For example: in the stories "Davron", "Falak" nevlay, sayerpoy

Conclusions and suggestions. In Tahir Malik's stories, space and time are also depicted as a whole. In fantasy works, heroes are launched into space, travel to foreign lands, but in Tahir Malik's works, they travel to history. In the fantasy story "Falak", the main character travels to history on a device created by Jahongir, that is, to the 15th century using a device called elalloma. The work describes the era in which Mirzo Ulugbek lived, and the scientists of that time. A fantasy writer must convincingly present a serious scientific hypothesis and idea as if it had come true. If a writer does not reflect the problems of the present era in his works, the social significance of his work will be lost. The writer always feels the era and time. Even when referring to the past, he imbues the work with the problems of today. Thus, the story describes the events of two times - the 15th and 20th centuries in parallel.

Tahir Malik's story "The Hunt" is a work of fiction. Through fiction, the writer observes our motherland through the eyes of alien astronauts and writes about the sad fate of the victims of repression. In the story "The Sky", Tahir Malik connected fiction with history. In "The Hunt" he also turned to history. In both stories, the experience and skill of the accomplished writer are clearly reflected. In the story, four people who were unjustly arrested and imprisoned in the same barracks meet. All of them are political prisoners, that is, "enemies of the people", but their worldview, thoughts, and beliefs are completely different from each other, and even reject each other. In the story "The Hunt" the events mainly take place in prison and the forest. Here, the prison and the forest are considered literary settings. In Tahir Malik's detective stories, prisons, state farms, villages, cities, forests, hotels, schools, and cafes are embodied as literary spaces.

REFERENCES:

1. Бахтин М. Вопросы литературы и эстетики. – М.: Художественная литература, 1975. – С. 234-235.
2. Жўракулов У. Назарий поэтика масалалари. – Тошкент: Ф.Фулом, 2015. – Б. 89.
3. Лотмон Ю.М. Структура художественного текста. – М.: Искусство, 1970. – 265 с.
4. Малик Т. Даврон / Танланган асарлар. 1-том. –Тошкент: Шарқ, 2004. – Б. 150-151.
5. Поэтика: словарь актуальных терминов и понятий / [гл. науч. ред. Н.Д.Тамарченко]. – М.: Издательство Клуагиной; Интрада, 2008. – 287 с.
6. Хализев В.Е. Теория литературы. – М.: Высшая школа, 2002. – 248 с.
7. Хурсанов Д. Лирик ва эпик турда хронотопнинг ўзига хосликлари // Хорижий филология. – Самарқанд, 2018. – № 2. – Б. 84-87.